

Authors: Dr Miranda Geelhoed, Professor Jill Robbie and Dr Amy Proctor

The authors would like to thank Dr Katherine Simpson and Professor Larissa Naylor for their contributions.

The LUNZ Hub's RESPECT Project

The interdisciplinary Rapid Engagement with Stressed Peatland Environments and Communities in Transformation (RESPECT) project is affiliated with the Land Use for Net Zero, Nature and People (LUNZ) Hub and is funded by the UKRI Land Use for Net Zero programme. RESPECT aims to produce data, methods, landholder tools and proposals for governance reforms to change agricultural practices on peatland. RESPECT brings together researchers across Scotland and England with expertise in the natural and social sciences, humanities and law. RESPECT will also produce the Peatland Triage Tool (PTT), providing decision-support for landowners, land managers, farmers and crofters (collectively 'landholders') seeking to undertake peatland restoration. Upon completion, RESPECT will be able to provide a solid evidence base, and tools to inform land use decisions in relation to the restoration and sustainable management of agricultural peatlands.

This response was drafted with input from across our interdisciplinary RESPECT Team.

RESPECT response to the Land Use Framework consultation

This document provides a response from the RESPECT project to the UK Government's consultation on a *Land Use Framework*. The response welcomes the ambition for a strategic, multifunctional approach to land use but raises concerns about the way the consultation document leans towards achieving multifunctionality through a land-sparing model, based on the idea that some land is set aside for environmental purposes whilst other land is used almost exclusively for production of food (as well as fuel and fibre). At its core, our response calls for place-based solutions; championing multifunctional approaches that are rooted at the local level and that seek to integrate farming and climate and nature benefits where possible. RESPECT highlights lessons from Scotland's land reform and regional land use partnerships, calling for strong governance, community engagement, and equitable access to finance to align environmental and social outcomes. Lastly, the response stresses the importance of historical research data for contextualising and addressing current land use challenges, and the need to improve storage, accessibility and ongoing maintenance of data sets.

A blogpost on 'Interdisciplinary Scottish perspectives on Defra's Land Use Framework proposals' can be found on the University of Glasgow, School of Law [website](#).

OUR VISION FOR LAND USE IN ENGLAND

Question 1: To what extent do you agree or disagree with our assessment of the scale and type of land use change needed, as set out in this consultation and the Analytical Annex?

Disagree

As an overarching framework for strategic spatial planning and the targeting of land use incentives, the Land Use Framework is of key interest to the RESPECT team. The outputs will be able to support implementation of the framework once in place, but the Land Use Framework will also inform our outputs particularly in relation to recommendations for policy and governance reforms.

In relation to the assessment of the scale and type of land use change needed – underpinning the Land use Framework proposals – we make the following observations:

- Categories 3.2 and 4 will significantly impact on farming (no or minimal activity) with the assumption that impacts will be off-set by increasing productivity elsewhere – based on the assumption that historical trends “of overall improvement in total factor productivity” will be continued. As the latter is concerned with the ratio of inputs (particularly labour) to outputs, this does not necessarily translate to absolute increases in productivity (increases in yields) that would

be required to maintain productivity levels based on this ‘land sparing’ model. Also, we raise questions about the *feasibility* of continuous productivity gains – in light of technological and environmental limitations, see also Q17 on the impacts of climate change including future flood risks in high productivity areas – and the *desirability* of intensification in certain areas in light of potential localised (negative) social and environmental impacts, as well as impacts on national policies (e.g., biodiversity in intensive systems if grazing areas are reduced).

- Peatland management and restoration is only considered in categories 3.2 and 4 which implies that responsible management of peatlands always involves minimal or no agricultural activity. We would ask for more evidence for this assessment, and we particularly note the absence of peat in category 3.1 which seeks to deliver both agricultural production and environmental/climate benefits. The [Environmental Improvement Plan 2023](#) (currently under review) explores new wetter modes of farming in peatland areas and research into paludiculture is being undertaken under the Farming Innovation Programme – have results been taken into consideration in the assessment?
- The spatial approach resembles the three-compartment model put forward by the [National Food Strategy Plan](#) by dedicating some land to the environment solely, intensification of production in other areas and more integrated uses in the middle. However, whereas the potential of integrated land use is significant (and key to delivery of the Land Use Framework considering its multifunctionality principle) the consultation is framed more in terms of land for the environment versus land for food production. In particular, separating questions of land use from land management (suggesting multifunctionality is achieved primarily in the margins or through agroforestry) disregards the wide range of agricultural practices (e.g., regenerative and agroecological systems) and their negative *and positive* impacts on the delivery of climate and nature targets. Where ‘land management’ will arguably be dealt with by a future Roadmap for Farming, the proposals miss an opportunity for development of a framework that truly integrates all cross-sectoral and sectoral policies relevant to land use and guide the development of (agricultural) policy and financial levers accordingly.
- There seems to be an implicit assumption in the consultation that environmental objectives are best achieved in low-productivity areas (with production moved to high-productivity areas). We raise concerns about how much the framework is equipped to deal with the biggest land use challenges where high-productivity areas include key priority habitats – e.g., lowland raised bogs in the Humber catchment? This is the purpose of the RESPECT research project which will produce outputs that can feed into land use decisions in this complex area, whilst also making recommendations for policy and governance reforms based on data gathered.

PRINCIPLES: TAKING A SPATIAL APPROACH

Question 2: Do you agree or disagree with the land use principles proposed?

Neither agree nor disagree

There is an inherent tension between land use decisions that are fit for the long-term and those that are responsive by design which is not recognised or addressed in the consultation.

We also note the key difference between the proposed principles and those put forward by the [Food, Farming and Countryside](#) Commission in 2023, including decisions being *locally responsive* and *contributing prosperity* to local communities. These principles go further than the proposed participatory principle of ‘co-design’ at strategic level, holding greater potential for creation of multifunctional landscapes that are rooted in local communities and economies, in support of a just transition towards net zero.

In this regard, a lot can be learned from Scotland which third [Land Use Strategy](#) 2021-2026 integrates the principles of the [Land Rights and Responsibilities Statement](#), emphasising community wellbeing and the need for greater collaboration and community engagement in decisions about land at local levels.

A number of initiatives (incl. policy/governance reforms) putting principles into practice can be mentioned:

- [Regional Land Use Partnerships](#) piloted in five regions aim to facilitate collaboration between local government, communities, landholders and other stakeholders. In the South of Scotland this recently led to the first [Regional Land Use Framework](#).
- Legal obligations on large-scale landowners to produce a publicly available [Land Management Plan](#) developed through engagement with communities, as proposed under the Land Reform Bill. Community bodies can also report a breach of this obligation to a new Land and Communities Commissioner.
- Scottish Government’s [Principles for Responsible Investment in Natural Capital](#) which state that investment in and use of Scotland’s natural capital should create benefits that are shared between public, private and community interests.
- Protocols and guidance by the Scottish Land Commission - a public body tasked with, among other things, embedding responsible land ownership and use – on how to involve [communities directly in decisions on land use at local level](#), and deliver public and [community benefits from land](#) including through [collaborative governance models](#).
- Advisory services within the Scottish Land Commission (public body) and Community Land Scotland (NGO) to support the delivery of community benefits from natural capital projects and support partnership projects with local communities.

Question 3: Beyond Government departments in England, which other decision makers do you think would benefit from applying these principles?

[Combined and local authorities \(including local planning authorities\)](#)

[Landowners and land managers \(including environmental and heritage groups\)](#)

[Others \(please specify\)](#)

Whilst it would be beneficial to apply principles consistently across all land governance levels, it is noted that it may not be straightforward for landowners and land managers to implement principles effectively within a fragmented policy landscape (with competing policy and land use demands). Implementation through alignment of policy and financial incentives will be key. RESPECT will work directly with landholders and other stakeholders in the Humber catchment to understand barriers and opportunities in law and governance to realising peatland restoration on agricultural land.

Question 4: What are the policies, incentives and other changes that are needed to support decision makers in the agricultural sector to deliver this scale of land use change, while considering the importance of food production?

The consultation graphics mask the complexities of multifunctional landscapes and the inherent tensions between land-sparing approaches (see Q1 above) and multifunctionality. Our preliminary work to help understand tensions between agricultural production and peatland restoration and management show that relations are not clearcut and depend greatly on the capacities and characteristics of the land and the specifics of agricultural practices in a place, e.g., habitat, hydrology, types of livestock (notably sheep/cattle) and breeds, and land use in adjacent areas.

The Framework should be revised so that it can more directly support practices (policies, incentives, other changes) that have the goal of supporting a just transition to multifunctional landscapes. Policies need to be

flexible enough to enable place-based, farmer-scale decisions to ensure a balance between peat health and agricultural production, taking into account impacts on local communities and economies.

Policies also need to go beyond a ‘food/farming versus environment’ divide, recognising multifunctionality within. Farmers’ produce more than food or other agricultural outputs. Socio-ecological public goods may include environmental benefits and cultural heritage, whilst acknowledging that the delivery of these goods is inextricably linked to a farmers’ primary function and identity as food producers (see this [policy briefing](#) by Proctor *et al*, University of Newcastle, on this topic). At the same time, environmental land uses are diverse and whilst some projects may focus on specific benefits/policy objectives (e.g., net zero/carbon sequestration) others may deliver a wide range of benefits. We are, in principle, supportive of policy interventions that address the environmental and social aspects of peatland management and restoration in a holistic way (e.g., public funding for restoration that focuses on multiple benefits rather than just area-based climate targets).

A place-based approach to policy development in support of multifunctional landscapes needs to be particularly mindful of the just transition implications of land use change that is driven forward at considerable speed and scale. There is a need for capacity building and skills development for both farmers and farm advisory professionals, to support changes in practices. Models of delivery could be farmer-led (e.g., on-farm demonstration, training events, farmer-led networks, peer to peer learning) or led by land advisory professional bodies through CPD, training etc. This is where co-design is vital to understand needs, demand and delivery.

MAKING THE BEST USE OF LAND

Question 5: How could Government support more land managers to implement multifunctional land uses that deliver a wider range of benefits, such as agroforestry systems with trees within pasture or arable fields?

Note our responses to Q2 and Q4 – this question and the consultation graphics signal a narrow understanding of *multifunctionality* in the consultation. We encourage Government to implement a place-based approach to developing multifunctional landscapes, recognising the potential for integrated land use through changing land management practices (bridging the ‘land use versus land management divide’) and for multifunctionality *within* agricultural and environmental land uses.

We also note again (Q2) the ambitions of the [Environment Improvement Plan 2023](#) to do research into/trial wetter peatland-based farming systems which is absent from this consultation.

A place-based approach exposes tensions between ‘top down’ policy interventions and those that are locally responsive (e.g., to the physical capacity of the land, social capacity of landholders, needs of local communities). Such an approach requires working directly with farmers to create a shared understanding of what public goods the land could deliver locally – supported with but not directed by external actors.

Question 6: What should the Government consider in identifying suitable locations for spatially targeted incentives?

The RESPECT project seeks to establish the current and future physical capacity of land in the Humber catchment to contribute to net zero and prioritise areas for peatland restoration. RESPECT will also establish the social capacities of key landholders (landowners, land managers and farmers) in the Humber catchment, as well as preferences of broader land interest groups (e.g., agricultural labourers, adjacent residential owners and tenants, community councils, environmental organisations and recreational land users).

Physical and social criteria/variables for identifying suitable locations are based on preliminary research only and include:

- Biodiversity change/productivity change
- Carbon storage
- Biodiversity/eco-diversity
- Financial use/value

- Social value for communities and for the public
- Flood risk/resilience and erosion risk/resilience (especially at the coast)
- Bio resilience

At this moment, we are not able to attribute a significance factor (in terms of our own view, and the view of landholders and other interest groups), but this will be a key output of the RESPECT project. A key component missing in the consultation is climate change, e.g., how does intensification change flood risks? Natural and anthropogenic acceleration of sea level rises are not mentioned. Changes in climate and sea levels will impact on highly productive areas. The latest [Environment Agency analysis](#) shows high levels of G1 farmland at risk of flooding and/or erosion. Rising sea levels may cause issues with salinisation and rising groundwater levels. Acids dissolving carbonates may also cause carbon release in some environments.

In addition to the physical capacities of the land, spatially targeted incentives should consider which areas could maximise socio-economic benefits at all (national, regional and local) levels. In this regard, a placebased approach that integrates place-based knowledge and considers local economic capacities and the needs of local communities is key to supporting a just transition to multifunctional landscapes.

Question 7: What approach(es) could most effectively support land managers and the agricultural sector to steer land use changes to where they can deliver greater potential benefits and lower trade-offs?

See Q4 above.

There is a need to better integrate peatland restoration into agricultural payment frameworks, avoiding conflicting financial incentives. This will increase the compatibility of peatland restoration with other agricultural payment mechanisms, recognising the contribution of peatland restoration to agricultural land.

Question 8: In addition to promoting multifunctional land uses and spatially targeting land use change incentives, what more could be done by Government or others to reduce the risk that we displace more food production and environmental impacts abroad? Please give details for your answer.

- Monitoring land use change or production on agricultural land
- Accounting for displaced food production impacts in project appraisals
- Protecting the best agricultural land from permanent land use changes

RESPECT will produce evidence-based policy recommendations that will be able to answer whether the best agricultural land should always be protected from permanent land use changes like changes required for peatland restoration. We are currently not yet able to answer this question.

- Other (please specify)

The lack of consideration for the need to change diets/energy use/consumption patterns as a solution for reduced production capacity (to meet Net Zero and Environment Act targets) is a significant omission in this consultation. Note Q1 in relation to our concerns about the *feasibility* and *desirability* of intensification of production in certain areas to off-set a reduction in production capacity in other areas. Where higher production capacity cannot be achieved within the UK (including through more integrated land management approaches) there is, indeed, a risk that the impacts of food production and other environmental impacts will be displaced if we do not address consumption as part of a national land use policy.

It is not sufficient to leave this issue to a potential future National Food Strategy. The Land Use Framework has the potential to address existing fragmentation across policy areas – which are amplifying competing land use demands.

Question 9: What should Government consider in increasing private investment towards appropriate land use changes?

Increasing reliance on private investors involves handing over power to make land use decisions to investors. This covers often very long periods that may exceed the lifespan of current landholders with implications for future generations as well as the wider community (e.g., minimum contract duration under the Peatland Code is 30 years but average project duration is more than 80 years). Where the proposed Land Use Framework includes a principle to be 'responsive by design' (responsive to new data, opportunities and pressures) it is unclear how this relates to the long timeframes and commitments of natural capital projects.

RESPECT will be working with landholders to assess the potential and challenges of peatland restoration pathways which will include different financing options. An increased focus on private investment (either by policy actively promoting private or hybrid options or through withdrawal of public funds) without an in-depth understanding of barriers for landholders and consequences for other communities and environmental factors is not without risk. This is particularly relevant when considered from a just transition perspective as, so far, groups like small-scale and tenanted landholders, and communities, have experienced obstacles in accessing finance.

The Land Use Framework is not clear on how markets, including financial markets, fit into its vision and how the principles are relevant/apply. How does an increased focus on private finance correspond with a more strategic spatial approach? If left to the market, decisions may not be based on the strengths of the land but rather the biggest economic opportunity. The Framework must consider investors' responsibilities in the context of land use (change), see e.g., the [Scottish Principles for Responsible Investment in Natural Capital](#) – these include the ambition that “[i]nvestment in and use of Scotland’s natural capital should create benefits that are shared between public, private and community interests, contributing to a just transition”.

Question 10: What changes are needed to accelerate 30by30 delivery, including by enabling Protected Landscapes to contribute more? Please provide any specific suggestions.

We note research on interactions between peatlands and legislation for nature conservation and protected areas (notably under the Wildlife and Countryside Act 1981). For adequate protection of peatland health, it is not simply sufficient for peatlands to exist in designated areas but for reasons for designations to include protection of peatland habitats to ensure their management is prioritised. Greater connections also need to be made between designations and net zero and nature targets, particularly in relation to the *restoration potential* of areas (as will be evidenced through the RESPECT project) which cannot currently form the sole ground for a SSSI designation. These issues that prevent an integrated approach to sustainable peatland management need to be addressed as measures are taken to expand protected areas. See notably on this topic interdisciplinary research undertaken by [Jenkins and Walker at Swansea University](#).

In addition to protected areas, we note the complete absence of 'Other Effective area-based Conservation Measures' (OECMs) from the consultation document. Only [7.1% of England](#) currently counts towards the 30by30 targets. The Land Use Framework needs to be developed in a way that integrates a new mechanism to formally recognise OECMs in England. There are important questions around how voluntary agreements/dedications from landowners will achieve adequate, flexible and responsive protections and how true multifunctionality will be achieved through use of OECMs. These questions need to be considered as part of a Land Use Framework.

[...]

Question 14: How can Government support closer coordination across plans and strategies for different sectors and outcomes at the local and regional level?

See Q2 above on Scottish initiatives that support coordinated land use approaches that also integrate community interests:

- [Regional Land Use Partnerships](#) and the recent first [Regional Land Use Framework](#) in the South of Scotland.
- Proposals under the [Land Reform Bill](#) for mandatory Land Management Plans for landholdings >3000ha following community consultation, to be made publicly available.

Question 15: Would including additional major landowners and land managers in the Adaptation Reporting Power process support adaptation knowledge sharing? Please give any reasons or alternative suggestions.

Yes

Extending adaptation reporting to major landowners can be a key step for assessing and managing risks of climate change. We particularly note evidence cited under Q6 on flood risks for high-quality agricultural land. We also note steps being taken in Scotland to ensure greater transparency and accountability in relation to the land use and management practices of large-scale landowners through public Land Management Plans proposed under the Land Reform Bill (proposals currently for landholdings >3000ha but this could be lowered to >1000ha). These proposals include requirements for community engagement, and community bodies could also report a breach of this obligation to a new Land and Communities Commissioner.

More broadly, we support an approach to adaptive management (including at landowner-level) that recognises that climate resilient landscapes naturally and dynamically adjust to our changing climate, requiring adaptation to be anticipatory or proactive. See in this regard [written evidence](#) submitted by Professor Larissa Naylor, University of Glasgow, to the Environmental Audit Committee.

Question 16: Below is a list of activities the Government could implement to support landowners, land managers, and communities to understand and prepare for the impacts of climate change. Please select the activities you think should be prioritised and give any reasons for your answer, or specific approaches you would like to see.

- [Providing better information on local climate impacts to inform local decision making and strategies](#)
- [Providing improved tools and guidance for turning climate information into tangible actions](#)
- [Developing and sharing clearer objectives and resilience standards](#)
- [Supporting the right actions in the right places in a changing climate](#)
- [Other \(please specify\)](#)

All of the above but we reiterate (Q6) that at the moment climate change considerations are not integrated in a comprehensive way in this consultation and the Land Use Framework proposals, so this should be the first step. In particular, we emphasise that the latest [Environment Agency analysis](#) shows high levels of G1 farmland at risk of flooding and/or erosion. This could significantly impact on the proposed 'land sparing' approach where a decrease in productivity in areas dedicated to environmental projects are off-set with increased productivity in high-yielding areas based on *current* strengths of the land – not taking into account climate change impacts such as flooding, salinisation and rising groundwater levels etc.

Question 17: What changes to how Government's spatial data is presented or shared could increase its value in decision making and make it more accessible?

[Updating existing Government tools, apps, portals or websites](#)

The availability of, and access to, spatial data from government and government adjacent organisations has significantly improved over time. For example, spatial data including flood risks, landcover and lidar for England are widely and mostly freely available. The introduction of MAGIC (Multi-Agency Geographic Information for the Countryside) provides a centralised online mapping resource to view and compare a range of spatial data from national trails to agri-environment schemes. In addition, there are links to view meta data for the datasets, which is important for individual interpretation and comparative analysis.

It is important to state how fundamental metadata is to the appropriate and effective use of a dataset, especially in comparative analyses. Clear details of collection criteria, modelling (if any) and uncertainties are vital for meaningful application of datasets to meet contemporary challenges. The use of clear and understandable language so that definitions and criteria are not ambiguous e.g., how is peat or peaty soil being defined, what depth is the peat deposit. These can have a significant impact on management and intervention decisions.

Changes to support use through private sector tools, apps or websites

In terms of research data, such as that we are using for the RESPECT project and which we will be 'spatialising', there are more issues than when we look at public spatial data. A lot of (pre)historic environmental data from historical research (prior to the last two or three decades) was not deposited in accessible digital data libraries but is held in old digital storage or is still in hardcopy format. Numerous databases of research data are now inaccessible due to software obsolescence or require not insignificant technical skills to reconstruct. This is compounded by missing or at best poorly documented metadata, which is not infrequently challenging to reconstruct due to the original researchers leaving the profession or passing away. This can make working with material challenging.

More explanation or support for using existing tools, apps or websites

Maintenance of data sets upon project completion should be a key objective. Initiatives such as the Heritage Science Data Service seek to address this for research data particularly relevant to RESPECT. Unfortunately, this particular initiative is funded for only 5 years, a short span where longevity and stability are key. This is an advantage that government curated data has. Otherwise, we rely on extra-national, and volunteer led data repositories that may lack quality control, are underfunded or are at risk from political turbulence, e.g., NeotomaDB is at risk from US departmental cuts in science funding. Here is a key role for government to play but this may require significant investment (including in people!) to ensure that land use decisions (and the policy frameworks within which those decisions are made) are based on best available data/evidence.

Other (please specify)

We flag the risk of over-emphasis of the potential of Artificial Intelligence. This neglects the fact that these models are not trained in a void and require accessible datasets to function. There is also an issue of 'AI contamination' – AI training on AI training on AI training etc. which leads to pollution of datasets.

As a project, RESPECT is innovatively incorporating seemingly distal and esoteric data, at least from the perspective of land-managers (e.g., ancient pollen), to address contemporary and future land-based challenges. So much of our understanding of the development of landscapes and land-use over millennia is based on this data. However, as techniques to interrogate this data advance, enabling potentially significant contributions to be made to the design and planning of increasingly urgent interventions, there is a lack of strategic design in collating and making it accessible in the same way as contemporary data.

[...]

Question 19: What improvements are needed to the quality, availability and accessibility of ALC data to support effective land use decisions

RESPECT has not used ALC data in its peat mapping as the dataset does not include details on soil composition. However, for developing land-management options for areas with significant peat content, e.g., potential restoration areas, ALC data is anticipated as being useful to identify where conflict may arise between different stakeholder interests. To facilitate its effectiveness, the nearly four decades old foundations of the ALC need updating. Degradation of land, subsidence and the improved modelling of effects of climate change into the future (e.g., flood risk and extremes of weather) undermine the accuracy of the current ALC.

We also noted that the original survey criteria recommended investigation of only the top 1.2 metres. In large areas of good agricultural land in former wetlands, buried peats may be missed but be in a zone of impact through land-management practices.

Question 20: Which sources of spatial data should Government consider making free or easier to access, including via open licensing, to increase their potential benefit?

In principle, all spatial data should be free or much easier to access if we are to enable decisionmakers (from policy makers to landholders) to make informed, evidence-based decisions on land use change. We do, however, understand that there may be commercial or governmental sensitivities around some datasets, but safeguards could be put in place, for example, through an opt-out system or by allowing a grace period for deposition of project data. Easy access does require more than breaking down paywalls - data needs to be stored and managed in accessible ways. This includes physical data.

Question 21: What gaps in land management capacity or skills do you anticipate as part of the land use transition? Please include any suggestions to address these gaps.

Development and planning

Increasing development and planning capacity to integrate benefits for peatlands could increase blended finance contributions to peatland restoration. It could also stimulate the demand for and supply of projects, which would in turn stimulate an increase in contractor capacity.

Environment and forestry

Increasing contractor capacity is essential to increasing the quantity and quality of annual hectareage of peatlands restored.

Increasing land use change capacity such as for farming and forestry is significantly predicated on addressing market and policy pressures on these sectors that are driving their intensification.

Question 22: How could the sharing of best practice in innovative land use practices and management be improved?

Online tools provide ways to support best practice in land use decision-making. RESPECT will produce the Peatland Triage Tool (PTT), an online tool to provide decision-support for landowners, land managers, farmers and crofters (collectively 'landholders') seeking to undertake peatland restoration. The tool will use the physical capacities and prioritisation of restoration areas (WP1) and social capacities (WP2) as baseline data for the Humber Catchment in England, and the Forth Catchment in Scotland. These data will be combined with AI and Machine Learning to enable the impacts of land use, climate and sea-level change to be quantified at landscape scale. Landholders' motivations to engage in peatland restoration (WP2) will be integrated into an agent-based ecological-economic model. This will simulate landholder decision-making at the farm-scale to participate in restoration schemes.

In addition to sharing data and learning through online tools, we recognise the significant importance of peer-to-peer learning opportunities (also Q4) in support of land use transitions. Capacity-building programmes that bring external expertise *to support, not direct* landholders can also have significant benefits, and we refer to [NatureScot's Peatland ACTION](#) programme which includes officers that are hosted in a range of local bodies such as local authorities, fisheries trusts and community trusts.

Lastly, we acknowledge the recently established National Estate for Nature Group, bringing together all major public, private and third-sector landowners. Whilst this forum could allow for sharing of learning at scale, we emphasise the need to integrate local interests – of farmers including tenant farmers and local communities – at every stage of land use planning. The absence of these interests in discussions on key objectives and minimum standards for land management plans with clear milestones for restoration, is not in accordance with the proposed co-design principle.

CO-CREATION AND ENGAGEMENT ON A LAND USE FRAMEWORK

Question 23: Should a Land Use Framework for England be updated periodically, and if so, how frequently should this occur?

Yes, another frequency or approach. Please provide details.

Timeframes should be coordinated with other key policies. In particular, where the Land Use Framework will aim to align land management incentives (including public payments), timings will need to allow for such a coordinated approach – e.g., in relation to the design of new agricultural payment schemes.

**Question 24: To what extent do you agree or disagree with the proposed areas below?
Please include comments or suggestions with your answer.**

- A strategic oversight function to ensure the right information and policy is in place to enable delivery against a long-term land use vision;
- A cross-governmental spatial analysis function to produce evidence-based advice on strategic implications across different demands on land;
- Processes to embed land use considerations in strategic Government decisions;
- Open policy-making processes in collaboration with research organisations.

Disagree

These areas are important but do not necessarily address the objectives of aligning incentives, joined up decisions, accessible and high-quality data and skills development. Recommendations have been made in this response that demand a role for Government to embed the Land Use Framework in different Departments and ensure that its implementation is adequately supported - financially and politically.

See also our response to question 9 – it is not clear how markets fit in the proposed framework and how land use change can be designed and directed in a context of increased reliance on private finance and limited regulatory restrictions/incentives to ensure that land use decisions are in accordance with the (current and future) strengths of the land.